

Do good schools really push up property prices? Disentangling school and neighbourhood effects with empirical evidence from Brighton, England

Josiah Tan^{*1} and Adam Dennett^{†1}

¹Bartlett Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis, University College London

GISRUK 2024

Summary

The influence of school quality on local house prices is a recurrent theme in narratives around housing affordability. A perception that proximity to good schools pushes prices up was one factor which contributed to a shift in the secondary-school admissions policy away from proximity-based criteria in Brighton, England, in 2008. But is this link as strong as many believe? In this paper we conduct a detailed spatio-temporal analysis of 81,000 residential transactions in Brighton between 2000 and 2019, demonstrating that good school proximity is less important than other contextual factors.

KEYWORDS: House Prices, School Proximity, Spatial Analysis

1. Introduction

In popular media and marketing narratives as well as the field of housing research, the theory that proximity to good schools makes housing more expensive is widely acknowledged. The causal pathways appear obvious – in a system where resource scarcity (good, free-to-access schools) can be high, and access to that limited resource is determined, frequently, by geographic residential proximity, then competition for that residential proximity will increase. As demand and competition rises and the route to winning is through paying more, then prices will naturally increase in this classical supply and demand scenario.

The literature from across the world is full of evidence that this theory holds in many different contexts but the strength of the association can sometimes be quite weak (for example Wen et al., 2017) with many studies hindered by data samples that are either relatively small (Black, 1999; Cheshire & Sheppard, 2004; Gibbons & Machin, 2003; Leech & Campos, 2003), do not account for property-level characteristics (Gibbons & Machin, 2006), or cover a short period of time (Cheshire & Sheppard, 2004; Gibbons & Machin, 2003; Leech & Campos, 2003).

In this paper we address these limitations with a detailed spatio-temporal analysis of house prices in Brighton relative to detailed property attribute data and other locational factors including proximity to schools and other neighbourhood effects. Brighton makes for a particularly interesting case study as in 2008, the admissions policy for its secondary schools was altered partially in response to a perceived house price premium near some of the more popular secondary schools. (Allen et al., 2013). Our analysis spans a period between 2000 and 2019 – crucially either side of the admissions policy change – and allows us to assess the contribution that school quality and proximity has on price fluctuations. We find that while schools have some effect on prices, other contextual factors have greater influence.

2. Methodology

To investigate the school effect on property prices, we use an established hedonic regression modelling

* josiah.tan.19@alumni.ucl.ac.uk

† a.dennett@ucl.ac.uk

framework, with some adjustments for spatial and temporal elements. We link properties and schools via realistic walking and public transport journey times along the road network to home locations and every sale is linked to the perceived quality of the nearest primary and secondary school when the sale occurred. To explore the impact of the 2008 admissions policy change, the final model splits the data into two panels of pre- and post- reform sales.

The spine of our research dataset is the new linked House Price (HP) dataset for England and Wales (1995-2021), created by Chi et al. (2022). From this we select 7 structural variables including price paid, construction year, year of sale, property type, floor area, number of rooms, energy efficiency rating and postcode, for 81,652 sales transactions in Brighton between 2000 and 2019, spatially joining them with neighbourhood deprivation, accessibility and school quality perception variables.

Perceptions of school quality amongst homebuyers are subjective but we derive a composite 4-level indicator of perceived school quality from Ofsted ratings, DfES data available on Key Stage 2 and 4 assessment results, Free School Meals (FSM) and pupil destinations. Accessibilities to schools as well as rail stations and the city centre are calculated using the Rapid Realistic Routing with R5 (r5r) package (Pereira *et al.*, 2021).

The general hedonic price model we use can be written as follows:

$$P_{it} = f(X_{ht}, X_{gt}, X_s, e_t) \tag{1}$$

where:

P_{it} = price of transaction i in period t

X_{ht} = a vector of property-level characteristics at the time of transaction

X_{gt} = a vector of neighbourhood-level contextual variables at the time of transaction

X_s = a vector of socio-economic characteristics of the neighbourhood assumed to be persistent over time.

3. Results

The map in **Figure 1** illustrates the spatial distribution of the house prices aggregated to Lower Level Super Output Areas (LSOAs) in 2019 (the geographical variation in house prices does not change much year-by-year). Higher prices tend to be seen in the North and East of the City Centre, with the LSOAs with the highest prices near Preston Park and Hove rail stations (**Figure 2**) and also near in-demand schools such as Blatchington Mill, Dorothy Stringer and Varndean. Proximity to good primary schools seems centred near the city centre and rail stations, with good secondary schools being located more towards the west (**Figure 3**). However, Whitehawk and Moulescoomb (red areas eastward of Brighton station are deprived in terms of both IMD and a lack of good schools.

Figure 1 Map showing average house prices in Brighton and Hove by LSOA (2019)

Figure 2 Contextual Index of Multiple Deprivation Deciles and Rail Station Locations

Figure 3 Walking Proximity to (a) Primary and (b) Secondary Schools in Brighton

The results of different models of housing attribute and contextual variables are shown in **Table 1**. The dwelling characteristics and time only model (a) accounts for 83% of the variation in house prices across the city over the 19 year study period. Year sold is the most important predictor of price variation, with Floor Area and type of property also important explanatory variables.

Adding contextual variables into the model, the R^2 is improved to 86-87%, but across the study period, proximity to ‘Good’ schools has a weaker effect than local Index of Multiple Deprivation scores or bus accessibility to the city centre. Proximity to ‘Good’ Primary Schools is more important than secondary

schools, but both are confounded by Electoral Ward (neighbourhood) effects. Wealthy Wards have the strongest positive influence on house prices and the most 'studentified' wards in the city, those with most negative influence on prices.

Running the whole analysis on pre- and post- admissions reform panels of 2000-2007 and 2008-2019 reveals that the removal of distance criteria and the introduction of lottery for secondary school oversubscription had little effect on the influence of distance to school on prices – if anything, proximity has stronger positive effect after the reforms.

Table 1: House Price Modelled by Baseline Attribute + Contextual Variables

Variable (Reference)	a) Whole period	b) Pre-reform	c) Post-reform
	Coefficients (t-value)		
Constant	9.103** (491.80)	9.289** (337.26)	9.715** (400.34)
Year (2000/2008)			
2001	0.180** (46.51)	0.180** (44.37)	
2007	0.835** (212.20)	0.833** (201.10)	
2009	0.726** (161.48)		-0.060** (-11.91)
2019	1.230** (274.03)		0.439** (86.88)
Property Type (Flat/Maisonette)			
Detached	0.307** (81.95)	0.271** (43.51)	0.336** (73.93)
Semi-detached	0.226** (76.46)	0.207** (45.72)	0.246** (65.21)
Terrace	0.192** (82.70)	0.179** (51.67)	0.206** (68.33)
Number of rooms	0.029** (32.51)	0.025** (18.14)	0.032** (28.35)
Log Total floor area	0.489** (156.47)	0.465** (99.99)	0.514** (126.13)
Energy Efficiency	0.0003** (4.05)	-0.00008 (-0.76)	0.0007** (8.57)
Construction Age (NA)			
Before 1900-1990	-0.022** (-3.17) to -0.093** (-13.36)	-0.023** (-2.04) to -0.102** (-9.89)	-0.030** (-3.28) to -0.083** (-8.98)
1991-2007 onwards	0.020** (2.34) to 0.136** (15.92)	0.055** (4.30) to 0.186** (14.77)	0.029** (2.72) to 0.085 (7.66)
Bus time to city centre (Not near)			
0-5 minutes	0.283** (11.87)	0.242** (7.67)	0.312** (8.57)
25-30 minutes	0.067** (14.72)	0.036** (4.90)	0.087** (15.35)
40-45 minutes	-0.007** (-1.98)	-0.019** (-3.31)	-0.002 (-0.45)
Rail Station (None)			
Brighton	-0.030** (-9.09)	-0.019** (-3.94)	-0.038** (-8.95)
Hove	-0.054** (-13.30)	-0.051** (-8.41)	-0.052** (-10.07)
Preston Park	-0.007 (-1.36)	-0.011 (-1.31)	-0.002 (-0.34)
Log Walk time to nearest rail	-0.044** (-17.12)	-0.048** (-12.48)	-0.041** (-12.04)
Walk time to nearest secondary school	0.0007** (6.49)	0.0008** (4.74)	0.0003** (2.05)
Walk time to nearest primary school	0.005** (29.37)	0.005** (19.21)	0.005** (22.49)
IMD Deciles (Decile 1)			
Decile 2	0.104** (20.34)	0.114** (14.90)	0.096** (14.46)
Decile 10	0.241 (39.21)	0.248** (25.61)	0.229** (29.79)
Proximity to good secondary			

school in year sold			
0-5 minutes	0.034** (2.55)	0.030 (1.20)	0.027 (1.81)
5-10 minutes	0.043** (6.74)	0.027** (2.51)	0.040** (5.09)
20-25 minutes	0.0009 (0.32)	-0.016** (-3.56)	0.005 (1.38)
25-30 minutes	-0.007** (-2.65)	-0.012** (-3.30)	-0.005 (-1.67)
Proximity to good primary school in year sold			
0-5 minutes	0.055** (10.83)	0.054** (6.63)	0.062** (9.63)
5-10 minutes	0.023** (5.96)	0.017** (2.64)	0.040** (8.10)
20-25 minutes	0.026** (7.38)	0.019** (3.33)	0.041** (8.91)
25-30 minutes	0.018** (4.66)	0.010 (1.76)	0.028** (5.82)
Electoral Wards			
	-0.165** (-23.58) to	-0.151** (-13.91) to	-0.178** (-19.90) to 0.051**
	0.052** (10.30)	0.045** (5.75)	(7.83)
Sample Size	73,559	35,256	38,303
Adjusted R ²	0.867	0.800	0.816
F-statistic	5110**	1720**	1980**

4. Conclusions

Evidence from Brighton suggests the perceived link between proximity to good schools and house prices could be over-stated as detailed spatio-temporal analysis in the city shows only a weak effect, less important than other contextual factors. Secular trend of increasing house prices over recent decades is part of the deception – simply buying a house a year later in Brighton will have a bigger impact on price than its proximity to a good school.

Neighbourhood effects confound those of being in a school catchment area – good schools tend to be located in less deprived neighbourhoods with larger houses and better connections to employment opportunities. Evidence from Brighton suggests these are more important than school effects. Houses in ‘studentified’ parts of the city see significant negative influences on prices. The ‘significant impact on house prices’ that the school admissions reforms in Brighton were predicted to have by Allen et al. (2013) was not observed in the data. Schools do contribute to the basket of services that influence house prices – in Brighton, Primary Schools more important than Secondary Schools – but their influence is not any more important than easy bus access to the city centre or general levels of deprivation.

References

- Allen, R., Burgess, S. and McKenna, L. (2013) ‘The short-run impact of using lotteries for school admissions: early results from Brighton and Hove’s reforms’, *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 149–166 [Online]. DOI: 10.1111/j.1475-5661.2012.00511.x.
- Black, S. E. (1999) ‘Do Better Schools Matter? Parental Valuation of Elementary Education*’, *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, vol. 114, no. 2, pp. 577–599 [Online]. DOI: 10.1162/003355399556070.
- Cheshire, P. and Sheppard, S. (2004) ‘Capitalising the Value of Free Schools: The Impact of Supply Characteristics and Uncertainty*’, *The Economic Journal*, vol. 114, no. 499, pp. F397–F424 [Online]. DOI: 10.1111/j.1468-0297.2004.00252.x.
- Gibbons, S. and Machin, S. (2003) ‘Valuing English primary schools’, *Journal of Urban Economics*, vol. 53, no. 2, pp. 197–219 [Online]. DOI: 10.1016/S0094-1190(02)00516-8.
- Gibbons, S. and Machin, S. (2006) ‘Paying for Primary Schools: Admission Constraints, School Popularity or Congestion?’, *The Economic Journal*, vol. 116, no. 510, pp. C77–C92 [Online]. DOI: 10.1111/j.1468-0297.2006.01077.x.

- Leech, D. and Campos, E. (2003) 'Is comprehensive education really free?: a case-study of the effects of secondary school admissions policies on house prices in one local area', *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series A (Statistics in Society)*, vol. 166, no. 1, pp. 135–154 [Online]. DOI: 10.1111/1467-985X.00263.
- Pereira, R. H. M., Saraiva, M., Herszenhut, D., Braga, C. K. V. and Conway, M. W. (2021) 'r5r: Rapid Realistic Routing on Multimodal Transport Networks with R5 in R', *Findings*, Findings Press [Online]. DOI: 10.32866/001c.21262 (Accessed 17 August 2023).
- Wen, H., Xiao, Y. and Zhang, L. (2017) 'School district, education quality, and housing price: Evidence from a natural experiment in Hangzhou, China', *Cities*, vol. 66, pp. 72–80 [Online]. DOI: 10.1016/j.cities.2017.03.008.

Biographies

Josiah Tan is a Planner at the Singapore Housing and Development Board and completed the MSc in Urban Spatial Science at CASA in 2023.

Adam Dennett is Professor of Urban Analytics in CASA, University College London.